

VALUE EDUCATION; A MUST HAVE TO ENSURE QUALITY EDUCATION**Caroline Lepcha***Research Scholar*

*Department of Eduaction Vinaya Bhavana, Visva Bharati
Santiniketan-731235, Bolpur, West Bengal, India*

Abstract:

Education is the only strong force which develops the personality of the students. It strengthens the mind and body of the student. Value education as the other names- moral education, character education, ethics education so on inculcates self awareness in students, so that one can be good to himself/herself as well as to the society. It also encourages conserving tradition, culture, religion and to be the better person so on. Quality education covers whole system of education, from the classroom to the outside school premises. Successful quality education has rooted in value based education and this is the major concern in today's world. To improve the quality education students should taste the fruit of value education.

Key word: Value, Quality, Education**According to UNESCO**

Values are generally long-term standards or principles that are used to judge the worth of an idea or action. They provide the criteria by which we decide whether something is good or bad, right or wrong.

Living in the world where there is full of confusion and less morality. The trend of the modern world called man with the value is outdated. Good thoughts can only find in the books. If we check all these years value is most needed in the fast growing social system. The fast transformation and growth in the lifestyle students become confuse and mostly fail to adapt the need of value. What is the simple meaning of value? Well, the dictionary means principles or standard, moral values, rule of conduct and ethics so on. When we look at the qualities that value carries, we find many characters and behaviours can be shape through it. Value helps to make students about importance of life, respect other fellow students, culture, religion, cast and creed. Therefore inculcation of values among students is very important in schools. Now how this value can be inculcated? For this the easiest and the fastest way is through the means of education. Everybody has the opportunity and rights to participate in the life of education.

Meaning of value and Quality Education

In the curriculum if value education is included makes a great help for the students in knowing what is right and what is wrong. Value education makes them aware for the negative influence and gives right platform to grow as a better human being. Over the past years value education has been the very important subjects in schools and colleges. Value education as names- moral science, character education, ethics education so on helping to shape and develop the behaviours of the students. Through value education a students learn to know what value is and where it can be applicable to.

The Indian national policy on education (1986) as modified in 1992, considered value education as an integral part of education and noted that (UGC, 2010): “The existing schism between the formal system of education and the country’s rich and varied cultural traditions needs to be bridged. Education can and must bring about the fine synthesis between change oriented technologies and the country’s continuity of cultural tradition. The curricula and processes of education will be enriched by cultural content in as many manifestations as possible. In our culturally plural society, education should foster universal and eternal values, oriented towards the unity and integration of our people. Such value education should help eliminate obscurantism, religious fanaticism, violence, superstition and fatalism. Apart from this combative role, value education has a profound positive content, based on our heritage, national and universal goals and perceptions. It should lay primary emphasis on this aspect. The growing concern over the erosion of essential values and an increasing cynicism in society has brought to focus the need for readjustments in the curriculum in order to make education a forceful tool for cultivation of social and moral values.”

Curriculum Cooperation (2003) *Value Education Study the Final Report* ‘Values education’ is broader and refers to any explicit and/or implicit school-based activity to promote student understanding and knowledge of values, and to inculcate the skills and dispositions of students so they can enact particular values as individuals and as members of the wider community.

Lovat (2005) *Value Education and Teachers’ work: a Quality Teaching Perspective* writes ‘What is Quality Teaching?’, that the inherent connection with Values Education becomes particularly and perhaps surprisingly stark.

Lovat, Toomy (2009) On *Values Education and Quality Teaching* states the relationship between Values Education and quality teaching can be expressed in terms of a “double helix”, a particularly powerful conjunctive term borrowed from the field of genetics.

Indrani (2012) *Importance of Value Education in Modern Times*, the definition of value education is educating the child to harmonize every aspect of his being viz. spiritual, physical, emotional, intellectual and psychological so as to develop his personality in a holistic manner.

Quality means *excellence, effectiveness, efficiency*. Quality cannot be seen as the quantitative expansion rather it needs a long term observation .so qualitative growth can be only seen through some improvements. Imparting education is not only limits the quality but how the students take that education and use it in the real basis that covers the whole quality system. Quality education is dynamic and it changes with the growing need of the society. For e.g. a student grows, his needs and interest also grows with him and this can be fully understood by the quality education and provides the facilities according to its need and interest.

Punke (1974) writes three aspects of quality in *Aspects in Quality Education* first is concern with procedure or goal; when development of certain procedure becomes a goal and second is to become master of his fate. Further in the third aspects he write is quality involves a broad gasp of the concept that in a complex society the individual improves his mastery and status in the universe largely through working with other person.

Inkoom (2012) conducted a study on *Implementation of Initiatives to Reform the Quality Education*. The objective of the study was to i) check the status of the quality of education ii) to investigate the effectiveness of education policy implementation and iii) how this has impacted on education reform. The result of the study showed that the low academic standards and low pass rate at Basic Education Certificate Examinations is the result of inexperienced head teachers, the lack of qualified teachers, low teacher professionalism, low community support for education and inadequate resources.

King (2013) writes *the Hindrance of Quality Education* are the removal of two exams, poor quality of joining students in secondary schools absence of science teacher in schools, lack of commitment of parents, weak supervision of daily performance, reduce moral competence of a new teacher, absence of dormitories of female children, absence of teacher's job satisfaction and changed of teaching from content to methodology.

Quality education covers the whole system of education- the school environment, school infrastructure, trained teachers, and school administration so on. If any of these fail in providing quality to the schools than it cannot be at mark of quality standard.

Importance of value Education in Quality Education

Schools have been the great source for inculcating value education from the very beginning. As value education has connection with quality education University education commission 1948-49 mentioned the various aspects of morality as: loyalty, courage, discipline, self-sacrifice and spirituality.

The Secondary Education Commission 1952-53 laid special emphasis on the following values in the formation of character of the students- efficiency, good temper, cooperation, integrity and discipline. Value education gives emphasis on the character building and this character makes the school of quality. Quality education is what parents, teachers, curriculum framers, schools administrators are looking for eagerly. Only the quality schools produce quality human being.

Quality education provides opportunity to the students and later on the students become scientist, technician, historians, and scholar so on. The validity of the inculcation of value is lifelong. The students with the value or moral awareness make inventions for the welfare of the human being.

Value oriented students later becomes parents and teachers through them the value becomes legacy. They consciously or in consciously pass on the value which was already in them. The part of quality education is included trained teachers and parents of good attitude.

Value makes the students aware and self conscious, when there is to choose between good and bad, students with value know what to do and off course quality education too does make the student of critical thinking and skilled human being.

Quality education facilitates the students for the development in both mind and heart. Hence value education promotes in good attitude, skills, conservation of tradition and customs and tradition so on.

In the clam teaching and learning environment through value education the students began to self-knowledge, which is one of the characteristics of quality education the student learn much more than the class room teaching.

Quality education is not only covers the schools but also grows with the student and goes outside the school environment. Likewise value education even work outside the school. When the students gets certain amount of knowledge and behave according to it and when his intra personal and inter personal skills becomes no harm to others in the community and the nature, there lives the value education and with the student.

Through value education the relationship between teacher and the students becomes strong as the value education teaches positive behaviour which is very helpful for intellectual growth in quality education.

Hence forth it is the part of the quality education.

Conclusion:

Here to conclude value education for quality education in schools creates as the bridge in generation gap. The students with moral values become much stronger in mind and heart to live the successful life. Quality education as the creator of development in the students can get good opportunity to develop character among students as well. Value education helps to reach the goals set by quality education.

References

- Curriculum Cooperation (2003). Value Education Study Final Report. *Curriculum Cooperation Study*, ISBN: 1 86366 578, Retrieved from http://www.curriculum.edu.au/verve/_resources/VES_Final_Report14Nov.pdf. Accessed on 25.03.2018
- Indrani, B. (2012). Importance of value education in Modern Times. *Education India Journal: A Quarterly Refereed Journal of Dialogues on Education*, ISSN 2278- 2435, Vol. 1, Issue- 3, Retrieved from <http://www.educationindiajournal.org/journal/63Beena%20Indrani.pdf> Accessed on 23.03.2018
- Inkoom, A.(2012). Implementation of Initiatives to Reform The Quality of Education in Rural Ghanaian Junior High School, *Edith Cowan University, Perth western Australia*. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111%2Fcdev.12048>. Accessed on 12.12.2015.
- Lovat, T.(2005). Value education and Teachers' work: a Quality Teaching Perspective. *The University of Newcastle Australia*. Retrieved from file:///C:/Users/hp/OneDrive/Documents/VES_Final_Report14Nov%20value%20edn%20australia.pdf. Accessed on 22.03,2018
- Lovat, T., & Toomey, R.(2005). Values Education and Quality Teaching. *Springer Science Business media*, ISBN 978-1-4020-9961-8, DOI 10.1007/978-1-4020-9962-5. Retrieved from http://www.curriculum.edu.au/verve/_resources/Values_Conf_020505_forum_address_Lovat.pdf. Accessed on 24.03.2018
- Punke, H. (1974). Popular control and Quality Education, *The High school Journal, North Carolina*. Issues, 58(2), Retrieved from http://www.jstor.org/stable/40365476?seq=1#page_scan_tab_contents. Accessed on 17.11.15
- UNESCO (1999). Teaching and learning for sustainable future. Retrieved from http://www.unesco.org/education/tlsf/mods/theme_d/mod22.html. Accessed on 24.03.2018

King , S .A.N. (2013). Investigation of Factors Hindering Quality Education in Secondary schools in Mbeya,Tanzania, *International Journal of Learning and Development, South Africa*. ISSN, 2164-4063, Vol, 3(6),1-12 Retrieved from <http://www.macrothink.org/journal/index.php/ijld/article/viewFile/4843/3915>. Accessed on [24.6.2016](#)